

The Interaction of *s-p*-Carbethoxyphenylalkylthiocarbamides with Bromine and a Note on the Effect of the *iso*Butyl group on Hydrotribromide Formation in 1-Alkylaminobenzthiazoles.

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In the course of an investigation on the effect of *meta*-directive substituents on the mobility of semi-cyclic amidines (*cf.* Hunter and Jones, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 2190), it appeared of interest to examine the bromination of certain *s-p*-carbethoxyphenylalkylthiocarbamides (I) in relation to the capacity of the corresponding alkylaminobenzthiazoles (II) for polybromide ion formation.

On treatment with bromine in chloroform under conditions in which arylthiocarbamides normally undergo thiazole cyclisation with elimination of hydrogen bromide, *s-p*-carbethoxyphenylmethylthiocarbamide (I, R=Me) gave rise to a well-defined hydrotribromide of ethyl-1-methylaminobenzthiazole-5-carboxylate (III), which yielded the aminobenzthiazole (II, R=Me) on reduction with sulphurous acid in the usual way (Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 2023, 2270; 1926, 1385, and later). Unlike the hydroperbromides of 1-amino-5-methylbenzthiazole (Hunter, *loc. cit.*), 1-methylamino-5-methylbenzthiazole (Hunter and Jones, *loc. cit.*), and 5-chloro-1-methylaminobenzthiazole (Dyson, Hunter, Jones, and Styles, *J. Indian. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 148), however, this bromo-addition compound did not undergo nuclear substitution in aqueous alcoholic solution.

It might have been anticipated on *a priori* grounds that the presence of the *meta*-directive carbethoxy group in the 5-position of the benzthiazole system would cause substitution at the carbon atom (3), and this therefore provides a further example of the fact that *meta*-directive grounds do not really favour *meta* substitution, but rather that they favour *o-p*-substitution less. This is of course embodied in the general conception (Ingold, *Annual Reports of the Chemical Society*, 1926, 134) that *meta* substitution is a residual effect produced by the disappearance of free affinity from the *o-p*-positions.

Both *s-p*-carbethoxyphenylethylthiocarbamide and *s-p*-carbethoxyphenylisobutylthiocarbamide (I, R=Et, and *iso*-C₄H₉ respectively) behaved similarly to the methylthiocarbamide, and yielded well defined hydrotribromides of the corresponding alkylaminobenzthiazoles on bromination under the usual conditions.

The *s-p*-carbethoxyphenylalkylthiocarbamides therefore differ from other *p*-substituted phenylalkylthiocarbamides in that the bromination of both the methyl and the isobutyl derivatives gives rise to hydrotribromides (*cf.* Dyson, Hunter, Jones and Styles, *loc. cit.*).

The effect of the isobutyl group in promoting hydrotribromide formation in 1-alkylaminobenzthiazoles appears noteworthy since *s*-phenylisobutylthiocarbamide itself gives rise to the hydrotribromide of 1-isobutylaminobenzthiazole on bromination in chloroform (Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 2951). Moreover, a reinvestigation of the bromination of *s-p*-bromophenylalkylthiocarbamides (Hunter and Soyka, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 2958) which will be published in the near future, has shown that the careful bromination of *s-p*-bromophenylisobutylthiocarbamide gives rise to an unstable hydrotribromide of 5-bromo-1-isobutylaminobenzthiazole which undergoes dissociation into the stable "dibromide" described in 1926, and bromine.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The thiocarbonyl chloride used in these experiments was prepared from carbon disulphide by way of thiocarbonyl perchloride, which was obtained by passing chlorine from a cylinder through a solution of 1 g. of iodine in 1000 c. c. of carbon disulphide in the apparatus already described (Dyson and Hunter, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1926, 45, 81r), until a gain in weight of 25 p. c. was observed. The sulphur chloride was decomposed by steam in the usual way, and the thiocarbonyl perchloride isolated by distillation.

Attempts to replace granulated tin and hydrochloric acid by zinc and hydrochloric acid in the reduction of the perchloride again proved unsuccessful. This is doubtless due to the fact that the former reagent carries the reduction beyond the thiophosgene stage. The yield of thiocarbonyl chloride obtained in this way, after redistillation was usually of the order of 25 p. c.; b. p. 72-75°/760 mm.

p-Carbethoxyphenylthiocarbimide was prepared by gradually adding a solution of ethyl-*p*-aminobenzoate (1 mol.) in chloroform, to a well stirred suspension of thiocarbonyl chloride (1.8 mols.) in water (10 vols.) at 15-20°. The chloroform layer was then separated and the excess of thiocarbonyl chloride distilled off along with the solvent from a water-bath, and the product recrystallised from dilute alcohol. The thiocarbimide formed very pale yellow glistening plates with the odour of aniseed, m. p. 58°, yield 70-80 p. c.

s-p-Carbethoxyphenylmethylthiocarbamide.—5 G. of *p* carbethoxyphenylthiocarbimide in alcohol (30 c. c.) were treated with 30 p. c. excess of a solution (33 p. c.) of methylamine in the same solvent, and the mixture was kept for a short time and then boiled for a few minutes. The solution was cooled and kept for 3 hours and the product recrystallised from absolute alcohol when the thiocarbamide formed aggregates of needles, m. p. 147-48°, yield 80-90 p. c. (Found: S, 13.6. $C_{11}H_{14}O_2N_2S$ requires S, 13.4 per cent.).

Ethyl-1-methylaminobenzthiazole-5-carboxylate hydrotribromide.—1 G. of *s-p*-carbethoxyphenylmethylthiocarbamide in chloroform (10 c.c.) was treated with bromine (1 c.c. in 1 c.c. of the same solvent), and the mixture was heated on a water-bath under reflux for 10 minutes, when hydrogen bromide was freely evolved. The solution was transferred to a glass basin and concentrated under reduced pressure at laboratory temperature, when a red gum was obtained which crystallised on scratching with a glass rod. The hydrotribromide formed small orange crystals which were crushed on porous earthenware and dried in a vacuum over potassium hydroxide and calcium chloride, m.p. 137-38° (decomp.). [Found: Br (total), 50.8; Br (labile), 34.0. $C_{11}H_{12}O_2N_2S$, $HBr(Br_2)$ requires Br (total), 50.3; Br (labile), 33.5 per cent.]. The hydrotribromide dissolved in alcohol giving a yellow solution, which evolved aldehyde after being diluted with water and boiled. On concentration this yielded a hydrobromide, which on basification with ammonia gave ethyl-1-methylaminobenzthiazole-5-carboxylate, identical with that obtained by reduction of the hydrotribromide with sulphurous acid.

Ethyl-1-methylaminobenothiazole-5-carboxylate.—The hydrotri-bromide (1 g.) was suspended in sulphurous acid (100 c.c.) and sulphur dioxide was passed through the mixture until a clear solution was obtained. On basification with ammonia ethyl-1-methylamino-benothiazole was obtained, which separated from alcohol-ethyl acetate in glistening plates, m.p. 169°. (Found: S, 13·6. $C_{11}H_{12}O_2N_2S$ requires S, 13·6 per cent.). The *acetyl* derivative, obtained by heating a solution of the base in acetic anhydride for a few minutes and diluting with alcohol, separated from methyl alcohol in white prisms, m.p. 174°. (Found: S, 11·6. $C_{13}H_{14}O_3N_2S$ requires S, 11·5 per cent.).

1-Methylaminobenothiazole-5-carboxylate.—A solution of ethyl-1-methylaminobenothiazole-5-carboxylate in concentrated hydrochloric acid was heated under reflux on a sand-bath for 40 minutes, when the sparingly soluble *acid* separated as a fine precipitate which was collected and recrystallised from a large volume of boiling alcohol-ethyl acetate. The carboxylic acid formed small fine white *crystals*, which were readily soluble in alkalis, and which were unmelted at 298°. (Found: S, 16·1. $C_9H_8O_2N_2S$ requires S, 15·4 per cent.).

p-Carboethoxyphenylethylthiocarbamide.—The solution obtained from *p*-carboethoxyphenylthiocarbimide (3 g.), absolute alcohol (15 c.c.) and 3·5 c.c. of a 33 p. c. solution of ethylamine in water did not crystallise after being heated to boiling point and kept for 3 hours. On concentration and recrystallisation from absolute alcohol, the *ethylthiocarbamide* was obtained in small glistening needles, m.p. 89°. (Found: S, 12·4. $C_{12}H_{16}O_2N_2S$ requires S, 12·7 per cent.).

Ethyl-1-ethylaminobenothiazole-5-carboxylate hydrotribromide.—*s-p*-Carboethoxyphenylethylthiocarbamide (0·9 g.) in chloroform (8 c.c.) was treated with bromine (0·9 c.c. in 1 c.c. of chloroform) and the mixture was heated for 10 minutes under reflux. The red solution was concentrated in a vacuum until crystallisation took place. The *hydrotribromide* formed small orange red crystals which had m.p. 103·04° (decomp.) after drying. [Found: Br (total), 48·8; Br (labile), 31·7. $C_{12}H_{14}O_2N_2S$, HBr (Br_2) requires Br (total), 48·9; Br (labile), 32·6 per cent.].

Ethyl-1-ethylaminobenothiazole-5-carboxylate.—The hydrotribromide was added to a large volume of sulphurous acid and sulphur dioxide was passed through the mixture until reduction was complete. On basification of the filtered solution with ammonia, the *base* was

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obtained, which crystallised from methyl alcohol in small glistening plates, m.p. 150-51°. (Found: S, 15.1. $C_{12}H_{14}O_2N_2S$ requires S, 15.0 per cent.).

s-p-Carbethoxyphenylisobutylthiocarbamide.—The thiocarbimide (2 g.) in absolute alcohol (10 c.c.) was treated with a 33 p. c. solution of isobutylamine in water (2.5 c.c.) and the solution was boiled and cooled. The isobutylthiocarbamide separated from alcohol in glistening needles, m.p. 107-08°. (Found: S, 11.6. $C_{14}H_{20}O_2N_2S$ requires S, 11.4 per cent.).

Ethyl-1-isobutylaminobenzthiazole-5-carboxylate hydrotribromide.—A solution of the carbethoxyphenylisobutylthiocarbamide (1.5 g.) in chloroform (6 c.c.) was treated with bromine (1.5 c.c. diluted with 1 c.c. of chloroform) and the solution was heated under reflux for 10 minutes, cooled, and concentrated under reduced pressure at laboratory temperature. The hydrotribromide crystallised on keeping in an evacuated desiccator over potassium hydroxide, for some hours and scratching with a glass rod, and formed orange crystals, m.p. 92-94° (softening at 90°) after being dried in the usual way. [Found: Br (total), 47.16; Br (labile), 29.6. $C_{14}H_{18}O_2N_2S$, $HBr(Br_2)$ requires Br (total), 46.3; Br (labile), 28.9 per cent.].

Ethyl-1-isobutylaminobenzthiazole-5-carboxylate was obtained by reduction of the hydrotribromide with sulphurous acid and sulphur dioxide as in the previous case, and separated from methyl alcohol in small glistening crystals, m.p. 133-34°. (Found: S, 11.4. $C_{14}H_{18}O_2N_2S$ requires S, 11.5 per cent.).

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